

CODE AND NAME OF THE MODULE:

BB-2208 HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

TITLE:

INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENT 2 CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

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Abstract/Executive Summary:

This case study analysis is not only be focusing on the description of the project about Syarikat Al Rasyid organization that known as an agriculture company that solely focuses on paddy cultivation but, as it is strongly connected with critical evaluation assessment which means to have an examination of a situation or condition with clear perspective and making proper recommendations. Case study that is solely to focus on Syarikat Al Rasyid organization and analyze various problems faced by the organization. It provides with many courses and constraints where are usually on real situations in order to solve the difficulties by making the right decisions. In brief, The main issues or problems encountered by Syarikat Al Rasyid is owned and managed by Muhammad Abdul Rasyid are lack of access to finance, shortages of infrastructure and machineries and lack of exposure This case study of Syarikat Al Rasyid will be using this Harvard human resource model to conceptualize the significant consequence of changes to operation upon human resource management outcomes. The Harvard framework for human resource management plays important roles to deliver better structure in managing the business operational efficiency. It is the framework for human resource management that consisting of six components such as stakeholder interest, situational factors, human resource management policies and outcomes, and long term consequences. Another reason is to decide and develop appropriate solutions in consideration of the model that have been selected for this case study analysis. After develop solutions to the identified problems, this is known as one of the final stage for this case study analysis where the most cases will be provided with solution's strength and weaknesses after selecting an optimal approach and a realistic assessment on the case study of Syarikat Al Rasyid. The last part of the case study will be provided and prepared with recommendations section to ensure the flows are in track and well organized.

Introduction:

Syarikat Al Rasyid is owned and managed by Muhammad Abdul Rasyid Bin Kamaruddin. It was registered in October 2016. Syarikat Al Rashid is known as an agriculture company that solely focuses on paddy cultivation. After completing his Belia Berpadi course in 2015, Rasyid began to open up this firm that the size of the land is about 1 hectare located at MPK Kampung Bebuloh. In running up the paddy field business operation, Raysid did not have proper educational background or relevant working experience in order to support or benefit his operations management and performance. Hence, he might encountered challenges and limitation in managing his business operation in paddy field due to the lack of depth knowledge or theory and practical works. The reasons on the benefits of having greater knowledge and practices are all of the decision taking when to implement any strategies and plan regarding the agricultural practices must be provided by appropriate knowledge and skills. For instances, in a way to refer when it comes for improving productivities and production of crop is entirely depending on the growth of the high quality of yielding varieties. This particular act requires the science theory and clear understanding on how to manipulate the process and its production method. In current situation, the modern agriculture also heavily associates the importance of agriculture knowledge and practices for the use of fertilizer, high technologies of facilities and infrastructure, drip system, greenhouses, devised irrigation systems, farm tools, tractor and post harvesting handling machineries. Therefore, planning supports the use of existing resource, workers and time in efficient, sufficient and effective ways (Alemayehu, 2014).

In order to Syarikat Al Rasyid management especially when it comes to its human resource management, thus the Harvard framework for HRM plays important roles to deliver better structure in managing the business operational efficiency. It is the framework for human resource management that consisting of six components such as stakeholder interest, situational factors, human resource management policies and outcomes, and long term consequences. Generally, this human resource model or framework is an important and beneficial model that help in explaining the role of human resource specifically be designed for the development of Syarikat Al Rasyid operational management business. Furthermore, the Harvard framework or model will precisely to explain about the role of human resource, how human resource gives better value to the business,

and how the business operation influences human resource management. The initiative of this model is to solve the various problems and challenges faced by the Syarikat Al Rasyid particularly for its human resource management

2 - Problem statement

The main issues or problems encountered by Syarikat Al Rasyid is owned and managed by Muhammad Abdul Rasyid are lack of access to finance, shortages of infrastructure and machineries and lack of exposure means that not many people know about their business. Thus these problem statement intends to prepare a better understanding about Rasyid's farm's motivations, challenges and constraint when managing the business. This is in order to realize the potential of the agriculture field as the beneficial force of the economy and to improve and develop the efficiency and effectiveness of Syarikat Al Rasyid farm business.

2.1 - The need of motivation to run a business:

In the process of running up the paddy field business operation, Rasyid indeed did not have proper educational background or relevant working experience in order to support or benefit his operations management and performance. Hence, he might encountered challenges and limitation in managing his business operation in paddy field due to the lack of depth knowledge or theory and practical works. This is where the motivation aspect plays important part of maintaining the presence of the organization which will always be survived to the local market for a long period of time. Meanwhile, the job market is competitive which makes Rasyid to see this as an opportunity that motivates him more to go outside of his comfort zones and decide the right he will choose for the best of his business. Another reason that boost his motivation is to contribute more towards the development of the country. Following the titah of the sultan that emphasized importance of agriculture in shaping the future of the country. The country is expected to be less depend on overseas products (imports). Thus Rasyid hopes to work harder in order to promote the country's sustainability

2.2. - Financial issue:

Most of the difficulties that became the main focus for Rasyid to work on it were financially motivate. At the beginning stage of his business, the government was able to provide paddy farmers with land that gave them opportunities to establish an agricultural company that focuses on paddy cultivation. Favorably, the LiveWIRE that known as a Brunei Shell Petroleum community development programmed which targeting local youth had given Rasyid the financial support with \$15,000 to help start-up the paddy farm business. Some of the problems that might arise was the cash flow difficulty which later followed with maintaining the business and have to pay employees and vendors. due to the high startup costs and expenses that In terms of obtaining surplus money to secure all the other costs such as facilities, farm tools and fertilizer were fully covered, Rasyid was most likely to have the great support and help of his family where at some moments be able to give him financial backing. In other ways, Rasyid would have to look for suitable investors, borrowed from friends or relative that left him with debt, making an agreement of bank loan. All of the financial supports that he had been received, it would been problems, limitations and challenges to manage the company. The reason for its stability because Rasyid had received unconditional morale and financial support from both of his parent which motivating him to further move forward the future of this business.

2.3- Soil suitability:

Another important issue is that, the land provided to Rasyid is not constantly fertile that lowering down the quality and standard of the land. The reason was that there has no earlier and proper inspection of the provide land to determine about its soil suitability an whether the land would be good to use for cultivating paddy. As result, Rasyid did the most of the work that toil long hours and performed it manually because the condition or states of the land was too damp for heavy vehicles and machineries to enter the paddy field. At some point, Rasyid's productivity and rice production had been affected greatly. The condition or suitability of the land unable the vehicles and machines made Rasyid to do extreme work manually where it supposed to be done by machines to bring ease during the working process.

2.4 - The lack of infrastructure:

The physical management of farm showed much difficult to handle due to the shortage of infrastructure for instances proper irrigation and sewage system. As to determine the condition of road which lead to the location of the farm, the road was badly-constructed which resulted hard to access the farm. Hence, improvement for the development needs to be reconsider with the irrigation system provided in Wasan. The current condition is not efficient and not enough as all of the nearby farms are also sharing it with each other. For all the workers or farmers whose working in that area should have equal supply of water, they had to separate and divide the time to have the same amount of clean water supply there. Furthermore, they have a Rota whenever they need and use the water and sometimes have to depend on the rain. To conclude about current conditions and issues, when it come for infrastructure for paddy farming specifically on land suitability and irrigation need to be focused on. It is also to reconsider on the importance of having easy access to start-up capital,

3 - Case analysis (Theory-driven analysis, The Harvard framework):

The Harvard framework is one of the most effective human resource models on developing and structuring human resource management of certain organizations. Hence, this kind of framework or model is currently be seen as a human resource model that acquires a more holistic point of view to human resource management. It is including the different measures of outcome in the business operation. Thus by using this Harvard human resource model to conceptualize the significant consequence of changes to operation upon human resource management results. The model as mention to have six components to steadily run the business such stakeholder interest, situational factors, human resource management policies and followed by its outcome, and lead to the long-term consequences of the organization

3.1 - Descriptions of the model:

The picture shown above is about the strategy model of Harvard model in improving human resource management where on the left part of the model starts with stakeholder interest. A Stakeholder means either organization, specific of group or individual who is strongly effected but the output of the certain project and they have an interest to bring a success towards the project which they can be referred to the within or outside of the organization that is being part of the sponsorship of the project. As a result, stakeholders can contribute a positive or negative impact on the project. These stakeholders consist of shareholders, management, employee groups, government and more. All of the interests define the human resource policies. At the same point on the left part of the model. There is the situational factors which affect these interests. Situational factored that consist of workforce characteristics, business strategy and conditions, management, philosophy, labor market, unions, task technology, laws and social values. After that, situational factors and stakeholders then influence human resource policies which incorporate the important components of human resource activities such as training, recruitment and reward systems. When it is a well-executed, human resource management policies can lead or result to positive human resource management outcomes and results. These include commitment, competence, congruence and cost-effectiveness which all of these outcomes will lead the way to long-term consequences and these can be either individual, organizational or societal (Vulpen, 2019).

4 - Alternative Solutions

4 - 1 Investigate the Developing Harvard Model in Long-Term Consequences:

Through investigations in order to give better solution for Syarikat Al Rasyid that will be focus on the developing Harvard model in long-term consequences. The asset of the organization based viewpoints of corporations defines heterogeneity in association execution by differences out in the public area of human resource management and its size (Hitt, M. A., Bierman, L., Shimizu, K., & Kochhar, R., 2001). As for stakeholder interests to find out about, matter to take for consideration is about the human component and to improve research conduction and hypothesizing more on this matter. Syarikat Al Rasyid should have a plan and strategy on achieve human resource management asset value that emphasizing on training, knowledge and abilities, especially for the stakeholder interest that influences business implementation. Therefore, human resource development and utilization results small amount of venture to succeed. It run down the effects of human resource management on employee's achievement and stakeholders interests, specifically on work improvement in public sector (Couch, K. A., 1992).

To highly concerning and providing solution about the advancement of Syarikat Al Rasyid human resource management and utilize practices for developing more worker skills in a way to prepare different type of skills, expertise and knowledge improvement. As a result, the development and usage of human resource management improves the effectiveness of organizational management that have competitive and capable employees. To simplify human resource development and use, it has to point out on the asset based on the focal view and human resource administration. Thus focuses on procedures and administrations several of tasks to accomplish visions and better results (Lepak, D. P., & Snell, S. A., 1999).

5 - Recommendations:

The efficiency of human resource management is about performing good practice because it give direct effectiveness of experience form the worker's perspective to put all into one viewpoint as a lesson learn. Even though it is no guarantee that the implementation would bring a success to the organization. Human resource practices are the most effective method when to assess the employee's attitudes and skills which could result in greater work environment and job satisfaction.

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